

ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF LABOR EFFICIENCY IN PRODUCTION

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Large-scale reforms are being carried out in the republic aimed at building a new Uzbekistan. "A new Uzbekistan is a renewed society that is changing, gaining strength and strength, becoming a free world." The primary foundations for building such a society, of course, go into the economy. Given this, the head of state noted: "The new Uzbekistan relies on modernized savings." Because without ensuring a stable pace of economic development, it is impossible to build a new society, to increase the well-being of people. If we come to an economic recovery, scientists and researchers will talk about many factors that provide it. Labor efficiency plays a big role in this series of factors. When accelerating the economic recovery, we must summarize and develop scientific considerations about the essence of labor efficiency, methods for determining it, and opportunities for improvement.

Social philosophy and labor efficiency in the economy are characterized as a concept reflecting the level of labor efficiency. It sometimes applies to the labor process carried out in an enterprise or organization, and sometimes to the process of social production that takes place in society. There are specific methods for measuring labor productivity in these subjects. Economists initially determined the efficiency of labor on the scale of an enterprise or industry, region or country, depending on the amount of production produced over a certain period of time. However, with the intensification of thematic scientific research, the methodology for determining labor efficiency began to improve. Today, it is determined not only depending on the amount of products produced, but also its quality, labor costs for the production of products, the amount of income from trade in products.

When discussing the level of labor efficiency, ways to increase it, scientists-economists apply the tone "efficiency of active labor," "efficiency of cash labor," "potential labor efficiency." It's no coincidence. Since, for example, the concept of "efficiency of active labor" allows you to reflect labor productivity at the enterprise or in the industry (as on a universal human scale). In thematic sources, it is proposed to determine the effectiveness of active labor according to the formula:

$$Pe = Vp / Pc,$$

at the same time: Pe – labor efficiency; Vp – volume of production; Pc – product costs.

However, the initial goal is not simply to calculate the quantity of products produced per unit of time. Labor is associated with finding ways to increase it, unrealized opportunities. And for this, if cases of unsuccessful use of working time and labor resources are suppressed, it is necessary to analyze from the very beginning how many products can be produced under existing conditions. It is this calculation result that is expressed using the concept of "efficiency of cash labor." In other words, the efficiency of cash labor is a unit indicating the volume of products that can be produced under existing conditions with the use of all opportunities. One of the founders of English cybernetics, economic cybernetics Anthony

Stafford in his article "Cybernetics and Management" recognizes the difficulty of determining the effectiveness of cash labor using the formula:

at the same time E_{cp} – efficiency of cash product; M_{vep} – maximum volume of products that can be produced under existing conditions; $P_{e/min}$ – minimum labor costs required under existing conditions.

- As for the concept of "potential labor efficiency," it is used in economic cybernetics to reflect how much products can theoretically be produced, relying on the conditions that exist in the modern period of social development. The potential indicator of labor joy determines how much you can hope for an increase in labor productivity.

- Scientific sources note that the decrease in the discrepancy between the current indicator of labor efficiency and the indicator of the effectiveness of cash labor depends on a number of factors. These factors include:

- • rational and efficient use of the existing material and technical base and production capabilities, steady diversification of production - as a result of which not only the volume and quality of production of products, but also its types will increase;

- introduction of innovations into production - as a result of which the entry of new scientific developments into production will be accelerated, the material and technical capabilities of the facility will be steadily improved, modern production technologies will be mastered, which will ultimately contribute to improving labor efficiency;

- on a scientific basis, rationally organize the production process - as a result of which it will be possible to identify new potential opportunities for the preparation of higher and higher quality products with lower labor costs, increase labor efficiency;

- reduction of work time losses - as a result of this, time will be saved for the performance of labor-intensive and unnecessary labor operations, performance of labor-intensive, unnatural actions, increase of labor productivity;

- development of skills and skills of employees - as a result, a certain balance is achieved between the qualifications of employees and the steadily expanding volume of professional knowledge, and the increase in qualified workers ultimately has a serious impact on the quality of work;

- improvement of working conditions - as a result, on the one hand, the possibilities of qualitative adaptation of labor functions are expanded, and on the other hand, the employee begins to receive satisfaction with his work, both cases are manifested in labor productivity;

- the introduction of a rational labor regime and guardianship - thanks to this, the possibilities of preserving the health of workers, the realization of their labor abilities are expanded, and an employee with good health and clearly showing his abilities becomes a factor in increasing labor efficiency;

- introduction of a system of fair remuneration - as a result, the employee's interest in the product of his own work increases, he is inclined to high-quality implementation of his tasks, his steady improvement;

- improving the psychological environment in the labor team - at the same time, healthy relations between team members are formed, these relations strengthen mutual understanding and benevolence, in these conditions the employee can competently and efficiently perform his labor functions;

- stimulating the creative activity of team members - as a result, on the one hand, innovations will increase, which can be introduced into production, on the other hand, the employee's interest in labor activity will increase.

Taking into account these factors, the efficiency of the labor of enterprises and organizations is gradually increasing in an organized society. Neglect of these factors, the use of repressive or voluntary methods instead leads to deplorable consequences. This can be seen on the example of the Soviet experience of the last century. During the years of Soviet power, labor efficiency for a long time was ensured by fear, pressure, and compulsory labor. In particular, the construction of the White Sea Canal, the construction of the Baikal-Amur Railway, the development of arid lands is a symbol of the efficiency of labor activity implemented on the scale of society, and the implementation of five-year plans in four or even three years is presented in the form of the enterprise's labor harvest. In fact, these were all labor products created on the basis of obligation. Directly, at the beginning of Soviet rule, he sought to organize these events on the principles of volunteerism. So, on April 13, 1932, a government decree "On the construction of the Baikal-Amur Railway" was adopted and began to be executed. The decree provides for the involvement of citizens of the country in construction in exchange for economic and financial incentives. However, the severity of working conditions in the taiga, food shortages, and a shortage of labor weapons led to an outflow of labor to other mines. Judging by the data, due to heavy dogs in one situation, when BAM needed 12 thousand landowners, only 504 people worked, instead of 2389 drillers - 50 people, instead of 5101 - 498 people. Then the government decided to apply the principle of obligation in the construction of the BAM and transferred it to the OGPU (state department for the protection of state security). The department immediately organized the Baikal-Amur camp and as soon as possible involved 32,411 prisoners in the construction of the highway. Thus, during the construction of BAM "labor productivity is ensured."

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